

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF COMPOSITES FISHING RODS

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies the bending deformation of composites fishing rods under the action of lateral load in consideration of the geometric nonlinearity. The large deflection and stress distribution of composites fishing rods are calculated and analysed in sectionally. Some experiments are carried out in the paper, and the numerical results obtained here by the nonlinear analytical method are shown to be in good agreement with experiments. From the studies of this paper, we can conclude that the nonlinear analysis will be necessary and suitable for the design of composites fishing rods.

Keywords: Composites, fishing rods, nonlinear analysis, large deflection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fishing is an interesting recreation. Now more and more people enjoy fishing in their free time. Fishing rod is indispensable to the fishing activities. The performance of fishing rod can directly affect the full play of fishing techniques. The traditional fishing rods are made of bamboo. Since the late 1950's, fiber reinforced plastics fishing rods have been in use. Today, the glassfiber and carbon fiber composites fishing rods are widely used and liked by many people because of the good water resistance, proper flexibility, light weight and high strength. In general, the composites fishing rod is a kind of pipe structure of which the diameter is very small and variable in each section, but its length is much longer than the lateral sizes. When the fishing rod is in use, it is usually acted by lateral loads, for example, its self dead weight and vertical fishing force at the thin end of rod. It is evident that the fishing rod will produce large deflection under the action of these lateral loads. Therefore, the linear theory can't be used for analysing the bending deformation and stress distribution of fishing rods, and the geometric nonlinear theory should be suitable at this time.

2. THEORETICAL STUDIES

For the sake of lightening weight and convenience to carry, composites fishing rods are usually designed into a sectional, contractible and hollow pipe structures of which the diameters are changeable along the axis of pipes and the thicknesses of wall are also not equal in different sections. (Figure 1). In the

analysis of this paper, three assumptions have been made: i) The fishing rods only have bending deformation, the elongation along the axis of rods is neglected; ii) The length of fishing rods is much larger than the maximal diameter, the effect of lateral shear stress on the deflection of fishing rods is neglected; iii) The composite material from which the fishing rods are manufactured is orthotropic.

Figure 1. The shape of Composites fishing rod

To simplify the calculating process, each section of fishing rod is divided into several parts, that is, the total length of fishing rod is divided into N parts, Approximately, the diameter and the wall's thickness in each part tube are treated as equal (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Simplification of Calculating Model

The nonlinear differential equations of fishing rod deflection under the action of lateral loads can be written:

$$\frac{d^2 w_i}{dx_i^2} + \frac{M_i(x_i)}{EJ_{z_i}} [1 + (\frac{dw_i}{dx_i})^2]^{3/2} = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad (1)$$

Figure 3. External Loads and flexure of fishing rod

Where :

$$M_i(x_i) = -P(L - x_i) - \int_{x_i}^{l_i} q_{x_j}(\zeta_j - x_i) d\zeta \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N; j = i, i + 1, \dots, N) \quad (2)$$

$$J_{x_i} = \frac{\pi}{64} [D_i^4 - (D_i - 2t_i)^4] \quad (3)$$

$$q_{x_i} = \frac{\rho g \pi}{4} [D_i^2 - (D_i - 2t_i)^2] \cdot \sqrt{1 + [w'_{i}(L_{i-1})]^2} \quad (4)$$

J_{x_i} — Inertia moment of cross section in each part,

q_{x_i} — Intensity of distributed dead load in each part after deformation,

E — Bending elastic modulus of composites fishing rod,

D_i — The external diameter of each part,

t_i — The wall's thickness of each part,

ρ — Density of Composite material,

g — Acceleration of gravity.

The boundary conditions are:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w_{i-1}(L_{i-1}) &= w_i(L_{i-1}) \\ \frac{dw_{i-1}(L_{i-1})}{dx_{i-1}} &= \frac{dw_i(L_{i-1})}{dx_i} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad (5)$$

According to the assumption i), the total length s_0 of fishing rod keeps unchanging, that is :

$$s_0 = \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{L_{i-1}}^{l_i} \sqrt{1 + [w_i(\zeta_i)]^2} d\zeta_i \quad (6)$$

Above equations constitute the flexural governing equations of fishing rod. In these equations, all the L_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, N$) are unknown numbers, but they can be obtained with the help of computer by iteration.

As soon as the values of L_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, N$) are known, the moment $M_i(x_i)$, deflection $w_i(x_i)$ and the tangent slopes of flexural curve $w'_i(x_i)$ can be obtained from equations (1) and (2). The maximal bending stress of fishing rod in every cross section is given by:

$$\sigma_f(x_i) = \frac{M_i(x_i)}{J_{x_i}} \cdot \frac{D_i(s_i)}{2} \quad (7)$$

and the axial stress is given by:

$$\sigma_0(x_i) = \frac{P}{A_i(s_i)} \cdot \frac{w'_i(x_i)}{\sqrt{1 + [w'_i(x_i)]^2}} \quad (8)$$

where:

$D_i(s_i)$ — The external diameters of fishing rod in each section.

$A_i(s_i)$ — The area of cross sections in each part of fishing rod.

and

$$s_i = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \int_{L_{j-1}}^{l_j} \sqrt{1 + [w'_j(\zeta_j)]^2} d\zeta_j + \int_{L_{i-1}}^{l_i} \sqrt{1 + [w'_i(\zeta_i)]^2} d\zeta_i \quad (9)$$

3. EXPERIMENTS

In order to verify the above formulas and compare the theoretical analytical results with the experimental results, this paper makes some experiments using the glassfiber reinforced plastics fishing rod.

3.1. Determination of Bending Modulus of Composites Fishing Rod

First, taking a section of fishing rod, using the three points bending method, measuring the deflection of the middle point at which a concentrated force is added. (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Measurement of bending modulus of fishing rod

Then the bending modulus of composites fishing rod is obtained by the energy method.

The total strain energy:

$$U = \int_0^{l/2} \frac{F^2 x^2}{8EJ(x)} dx + \int_{l/2}^l \frac{F^2 (l-x)^2}{8EJ(x)} dx \quad (10)$$

The deflection at loaded point:

$$f = \frac{\partial U}{\partial F} = \frac{F}{4E} \left[\int_0^{l/2} \frac{x^2}{J(x)} dx + \int_{l/2}^l \frac{(l-x)^2}{J(x)} dx \right] \quad (11)$$

that is

$$E = \frac{F}{4f} \left[\int_0^{l/2} \frac{x^2}{J(x)} dx + \int_{l/2}^l \frac{(l-x)^2}{J(x)} dx \right] \quad (12)$$

where f is measured by experiment when the concentrated force acted on this point is F , and $J(x)$ is the inertia moment of cross section.

$$J(x) = \frac{\pi}{64} \{ D^4(x) - [D(x) - 2t(x)]^4 \} \quad (13)$$

$$D(x) = D_1 + (D_2 - D_1) \frac{x}{l} \quad (14)$$

$$t(x) = t_1 + (t_2 - t_1) \frac{x}{l} \quad (15)$$

In equation (14) and (15), D_1, t_1 and D_2, t_2 are the external diameter and wall's thickness on the cross section 1-1 and cross section 2-2 respectively (Figure 4). The bending modulus of GFRP fishing rod measured by experiment is shown in Table 1.

3.2. The Measurement of Material Density

If the dead weight of fishing rod is considered in the analysis of deflection, the density of this material must be known. First, measuring the sizes of each section of rod, the volume of each section rod is:

$$V_i = \int_0^{s_i} A_i(x) dx = \frac{\pi}{4} \int_0^{s_i} \{D^2(x) - [D(x) - 2t(x)]^2\} dx \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, M) \quad (16)$$

where s_i is the length of each section of fishing rod.

Secondly, measuring the quality m_i of each section of fishing rod respectively, then the density of this kind of material is given by

$$\rho = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{m_i}{V_i} \quad (17)$$

The density of GFRP fishing rod measured by this experimental process is shown in Table 1.

3. 3. The Measurement of Deflection

In experiments of this paper, a three sectional glassfiber reinforced plastics fishing rod is used, the total length of which is 2420mm. Make a horizontal clamping support at the thick end of fishing rod, and let the thin end be free. The deflection at free end produced only by the dead weight of fishing rod and the deflection produced by both dead weight and a vertical fishing force (0.784N) at the thin end of fishing rod are measured respectively, The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The properties of GFRP and the deflections of GFRP fishing rod by experiments

Experimental items	Results
Bending modulus E	$2.434 \times 10^4 \text{MPa}$
Density ρ	$1.752 \times 10^{-3} \text{kg/cm}^3$
Maximal deflection (only by dead weight)	71.0mm
Maximal deflection (by both dead weight and fishing force $P=0.784\text{N}$)	706.0mm

4. EXAMPLES AND ANALYSIS

According to the preceding method and process of theoretical analysis, the computer programs are edited. Adopting the experimental data and analysing the same fishing rod as in experiments, the flexural curves and the maximal deflections in different conditions are obtained and shown in Figure 5.

1—only dead weight considered,
 2—only a vertical fishing force considered,
 3—both dead weight and fishing force considered.
 Figure 5. The flexural curves of fishing rod.

From Figure 5, we can find the maximal deflection produced only by the dead weight of fishing rod is 73.9mm, Compared with the experimental result 71mm, the relative error is less than 4.1%. If we compare the maximal deflection 691.2mm produced by both dead weight and vertical fishing force with the experimental result 706mm measured in the same condition. we shall come to that the relative error is only 2.1%. It can be seen that the theoretical results are in good agreement with experiments.

Making a further analysis, we obtained the maximal bending stresses and the axial tensional stresses in each cross sections. The stress distributions along the axis of fishing rod are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

①: 61.0MPa, ②: 24.7MPa, ③: 28.0MPa, ④: 20.0MPa, ⑤: 22.0MPa

Figure 6. The maximal bending stress distribution along the axis of fishing rod ($P=0.784N$)

①: 0.35MPa ②: 0.034MPa ③: 0.018MPa

Figure 7. The axial tensional stress distribution along the axis of fishing rod ($P=0.784N$)

Compared the bending stresses in Figure 6 with the axial stresses in Figure 7, the latter are much less than the former. Therefore, it is reasonable to neglect the effect of axial stresses on the analysis and design of fishing rods. On the other hand, the bending stresses, as shown in Figure 6, have a sudden change at the joint of every two section of rods. It is unfavourable and, at the same time, inevitable because the diameters of every section rod must be different each other so that every two section of rods can be jointed. But, according to the calculating method given by this paper, we can make the stress distribution curve become more smooth through adjusting the sizes of each section of rod. Furthermore, the most reasonable stiffness distribution along the axis of fishing rod will be obtained by the same methods. It is absolutely necessary for us to make optimizing design of composites fishing rods.

References

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